

REVEALING THE EFFECT OF CRUMPLING ON THE REINFORCEMENT EFFICIENCY OF GRAPHENE IN COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A graphene/PMMA model composite has been studied primarily using Raman spectroscopy, as the characteristic Raman band positions are closely correlated to the strain in graphene. Different from the conventional work, in this work, the graphene/PMMA model composite has been annealed to induce a residual compression, which leads to the formation of crumples in the graphene. Our main target is to study how the structure of the crumples affects the stress transfer from the matrix to graphene, and this has been achieved by comparing the strain applied to the substrate, with the strain in the graphene flake.

1 INTRODUCTION

Because of its exceptional properties, graphene-based materials have been extensively studied as fillers in nanocomposites [1]. However, many of the properties, especially the mechanical properties and the electrical conductivity, rely strongly on the conformation of the graphene flakes. Many of the theoretical values were calculated assuming a perfectly flat graphene layer, which may not be practical in real world because of difficulties in the preparation procedure. This could potentially explain why the performance of graphene nanocomposite is usually under theoretical estimation, as summarized elsewhere [1]. For example, when graphene is used to reinforce a polymer matrix, the 'effective' modulus calculated using the 'rule of mixtures' is usually lower than the theoretical Young's modulus of graphene ~ 1000 GPa [2], even if graphene or graphene oxide flakes display relatively large lateral dimensions [3]. It was proposed that the crumpling of the flakes not only significantly reduce the lateral dimensions, but can also create defects which induce stress concentration [3]. The potentially worse situation is when the flakes are highly scrolled [4], it is more difficult for the large polymer molecules to fully attach and wet the graphene flakes, a fact that compromises remarkably the potential of graphene as a reinforcement. It was not until recently that the scientific community started to investigate how this seemingly negative aspects of graphene can actually be utilized positively in order to enhance the performance of the composites or provide potential multifunctional properties [5]. In spite of this, the fundamental understanding of how the crumpling of graphene affects its capability, especially as reinforcement, is still of great importance.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

Graphene was mechanically exfoliated using the 'Scotch tape' method and was deposited onto PMMA beams to prepare the graphene/PMMA model composites [6]. Before depositing graphene, the PMMA beams were cleaned and etched by using UV-Ozone. The graphene/PMMA model composites were bent with a four-point bending rig, with the strain being measured by strain gauges attached adjacent to the graphene flake [7]. Optical image was obtained by using a Nikon Eclipse LV100ND microscope. Atomic force microscope (AFM) images were obtained in the tapping mode by using Dimension 3100 (Bruker). The Raman spectra were obtained using Horiba LabRAM HR Evolution equipped with a laser with $\lambda = 488$ nm.

3 RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

In Fig. 1(a) the optical image shows a graphene flake with the lateral dimension around 30 μm along the stretching direction as indicated by the white arrow. A Raman spectrum taken from this flake is shown in Fig.1(b), and the high intensity ratio of the 2D band ($\sim 2700\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and G band ($\sim 1580\text{ cm}^{-1}$) indicates that it is a monolayer graphene flake [8].

Figure 1: (a) The optical image and (b) the Raman spectrum of the monolayer graphene flake.

Graphene has been stretched in the direction shown by an arrow in Fig.1(a). The 2D band position of the Raman spectrum taken in the middle of the flake as a function of strain is represented by the solid red squares in Fig.2. The Raman band position has been demonstrated to be closely correlated to the strain in graphene, using the knowledge of the Grüneisen parameter [9-11]. In our case, the 2D band position down-shifts linearly with the applied strain with a rate of $-52.2\text{ cm}^{-1}/\%$, between the 0 and 0.15% strain regime. Even though the shift rate drops after 0.15%, perhaps due to a partially slippery interface, the value of $-52.2\text{ cm}^{-1}/\%$ obtained before 0.15% is in agreement with other experimental results [9, 12] hence can be used as a calibration, to correlate the Raman 2D band position to the strain in the graphene, as shown in the right axis of Fig.2. Accordingly, it can be seen that beyond strain of 0.15%, the strain in the graphene is lower than the applied strain, which again implies a weakened interface, due to the variable stress transfer efficiency, as will be discussed in due course. After reaching the strain of 0.25%, the sample was unloaded, and the 2D band position returned to the original position.

In the next step, the sample was annealed at $110\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and then cooled to room temperature, after which it was found that the 2D band position slightly up-shifts, indicating a residual compressive strain (Fig. 2). The graphene flake was deformed again for a 2nd cycle. In contrast to the 1st cycle, the strain in the graphene (as shown with the solid blue circles in Fig. 2) increases at a rate slower than the applied strain, until the strain $\sim 0.5\%$, after which the shift rate starts to increase, with a similar shift rate as before 0.15% in the 1st cycle. The increment of strain in the graphene is approximately the same as that of the applied strain, as indicated with the dashed green line with a slope of -1 (right axis of Fig. 2). This consistence only occurs at the beginning of the 1st cycle and the end of 2nd cycle, demonstrating that at those two levels, the strain applied to the matrix can be completely transferred into the middle of the graphene flake.

Figure 2: Raman 2D band position (left axis) and converted strain in the graphene (right axis) as a function of the applied strain. The dashed green line is a guide to eyes to indicate the constancy of the applied strain and strain in graphene.

To fully elucidate this behavior, Raman spectroscopy has been used to map across the graphene flake as shown in Fig.3. It can be seen that before being stretched for the 1st cycle (Fig.3a), the strain in the graphene flake stays almost zero, apart from the compression at the right edge of the flake. When the flake was stretched, the strain builds up from the edge and eventually reaches the plateau at the central region of the flake. This phenomenon can be explained by the well-established shear-lag theory [12], of which the expression is shown as below:

$$\varepsilon_r = \varepsilon_m \left[1 - \frac{\cosh\left(\frac{ns}{l}x\right)}{\cosh\left(\frac{ns}{2}\right)} \right] \quad (1)$$

$$n = \sqrt{\frac{2G_m}{E_{gra}} \left(\frac{t_{gra}}{t_m} \right)} \quad (2)$$

where ε_m is the matrix strain and ε_r is the strain of graphene as a function of position x along the flake with a length of l . G_m and E_{gra} are the shear modulus of the polymer substrate and the Young's modulus of graphene, and t_{gra} and t_m are the thickness of graphene and the representative volume element, respectively. $s = l/t_{gra}$ is defined as the aspect ratio of graphene.

In Fig.3(a) and (b), the open shapes correspond to the values obtained at the indicated 'applied strain', while the solid curves were obtained using 'shear-lag' theory to best match the strain of graphene. The stress transfer efficiency is indicated by the value of ns , which depends on the aspect ratio of the graphene flake [12]. In Fig.3(a), an $ns = 10$ value is used in the 'shear-lag' curves. As it was shown in Fig.2, the stress can be transferred efficiently only below the strain of $\sim 0.15\%$ and this can also be observed in Fig.3, where the strain plateau in graphene equals the applied strain. After 0.15% , the mismatch of the strain in graphene ($\sim 0.2\%$) and the applied strain (0.25%) suggests a softened interface. When the flake was unloaded, the strain went back to 0% , indicating an intact interface, though it is not strong enough to fully transfer the load from matrix.

After being annealed and cooled, the sample was again mapped using Raman spectroscopy. Prior to the 2nd cycle of deformation, the strain of graphene slightly dropped to around -0.05%, indicating the residual compressive strain. This is because of the thermal mismatch occurred during the annealing between graphene (coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) as $-8.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ [13]) and PMMA ($80 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ [14]) induced a $\sim 0.8\%$ pre-strain to the graphene, numerically in agreement with those studies on carbon nanotube nanocomposites [15]. Under this pre-strain, the graphene is still stable without apparent buckling (Fig.3(b)), but may crumple to comprise the compressive strain as predicted [16]. However, the calculated compressive strain of $\sim 0.8\%$ is significantly higher than the 0.05% compressive strain as observed, possibly due to the re-arrangement of flake geometry following the roughened surface of the PMMA substrate, as shown in the AFM height profile in Fig. 3(c) and (d).

Figure 3: The strain distribution of the graphene flake of (a) 1st cycle deformation and (b) 2nd cycle deformation. The open shapes are the strain in graphene, with the applied strain also indicated as inset. The solid lines are the estimated strain distributions (assuming no crumpling) using ‘shear-lag’ theory. (c) AFM images of the graphene and (d) the height profile along the red line in (c).

The sample was deformed for the 2nd cycle (Fig. 3(b)), with the solid lines being simulated using $ns = 30$ in the shear-lag theory, thus implying an enhanced interface and improved stress transfer efficiency after annealing. Different from the 1st cycle, the strain in graphene almost had not increased until an applied strain of 0.25%, while it started to build up at an applied strain of $\sim 0.5\%$, which is equivalent to around 0.2% of real graphene strain if the effects of the softened interface and the thermal mismatch are taken into account. Further stretching the sample to a strain of 0.8% and 1%, the maximum strain of graphene increases to around 0.5% and 0.72% respectively, and match well with the strain distribution estimated using ‘shear-lag’ theory on the basis of the corresponding strain level. Although the ‘applied strain’ and ‘strain of graphene’ are still not equivalent to each other because of the strain release at the initial stage due to the residual stress from thermal mismatch, after the applied strain over 0.5%, the increment of the two strains are the same, with the difference being always around 0.3%, as it can be also indicated in Fig.2. This $\sim 0.3\%$ strain difference comes from the strain release stage up to $\sim 0.25\%$, consistent with the previous studies [15, 17], possibly indicating that the deformation mode is the flattening of the flake [18] instead of the stretching of the C-C bond [19] at

lower strain. The pre-strains in the present work are similar to those obtained using AFM cantilever indenting freestanding graphene flake [20], and a strain of $\sim 0.3\%$ suffices to release the pre-strain and thus flatten the graphene flake. This not only proves the flattening of crumpled graphene during early stage of stretching, but also will be able to show how this graphene flattening affects the reinforcement capability of graphene in composites.

At higher strain, in the middle of the flake, a concave region occurs showing a less strained region than the other part of the flake (Fig.3(b)), and it is where crumpling is taking place either in graphene or in the substrate (Fig.3(d)). Different from a complete interface failure or graphene crack, where a sharp strain drop takes place [6, 21], the crumpling will only lead to a moderate strain drop in a relatively larger region [21]. This crumpled region stops the stress from being transferred to the flake efficiently, and a $\sim 0.1\%$ difference between the measured strain and the estimated strain plateau can be observed. Additionally, it can be found that the critical length at the right side of the flake is almost more than double of that of the left part, possibly also as a result of the crumpling.

The area underneath the strain distribution curve is also an indication of the reinforcement efficiency. For a perfect reinforcement, assuming there is no edge effect (shear-lag phenomenon), the strain of the filler will be identical to that applied to the matrix, therefore, the reinforcement that the filler provides will be 100% of the product of the strain and the Young's modulus. However, realistically, the edge effect applies so the reinforcement capability at the edges drops; hence it is always less than 100% regardless the size/length. In this work, the reinforcement efficiency (η_c) can be regarded as the proportion of the area under the real strain distribution curve, to that under the estimated curve using shear-lag theory. It can be seen in Fig.4 that the η_c increases as strain, indicating a further flattening of graphene flake.

Figure 4: The reinforcement efficiency η_c calculated for the applied strain of 0.5, 0.8 and 1.0%.

Further, an analytical model is proposed to interpret the effect of crumpling. As an approximation, the effect of the crumple on η_c can be converted to the misorientation of the ideally flat graphene given the side of the graphene flake is regarded as the 1D analogy. Following the analysis of orientation on fibrous fillers, the effect of misorientation can be expressed using the Krenchel orientation factor η_o [22], as the function of θ , which is the angle between the stress direction and the fibre axis. a_n is the proportion of the fibres lying at this angle θ :

$$\eta_o = \sum a_n \cdot \cos^4 \theta = \eta_c \quad (3)$$

On this basis, if each small representative element in the crumpled graphene flake is approximated as straight part that lies at an angle to the stress direction [23, 24], the effect of crumpling on η_c is the same as that in η_o (Eq.3), and defined as the ratio of the reinforcement of a crumpled graphene to that

of its flat counterpart, along the stress direction. It is expected that if the crumpled graphene is stretched to its full length it should provide identical reinforcement as the flat flake with same size.

Figure 5: Schematic diagram of (a) the cross section of a crumpled graphene flake. A crumpled graphene (b) fully and (c) partially attached to a crumpled substrate.

If the side of a monolayer graphene is expressed as the sinusoidal function y with wavelength λ and amplitude a (Fig.5(a)), then:

$$y = a \sin \frac{2\pi x}{\lambda} \quad (4)$$

$$\tan \theta = \frac{dy}{dx} = \frac{2\pi a}{\lambda} \cos \frac{2\pi x}{\lambda} \quad (5)$$

Hence Eq. 3 can be modified, where ds is the arc-length at x (Fig. 5(a)), as:

$$\eta_c = \frac{\int \cos^4 \theta ds}{\int ds} = \frac{\int_0^\lambda \left(\left(\frac{2\pi a}{\lambda} \cos \frac{2\pi x}{\lambda} \right)^2 + 1 \right)^{-\frac{3}{2}} dx}{\int ds} = \frac{1}{1 + (2\pi a / \lambda)^2} \quad (6)$$

As shown in the AFM in Fig. 3(d), if a is taken as 10 nm, and λ as 25 μm , $\eta_c \approx 1$, still underestimates the $\sim 0.1\%$ strain difference in Fig.3(b), hence a simple situation as described in (Fig.5(b)) is less likely to be the reason for the $\sim 0.1\%$ strain difference. Considering the increasing η_c at higher strain in Fig.4, the major mechanism has been proposed as, the graphene generally shows a crumpled geometry following the crumpled substrate surface, but locally some of part of the graphene are suspended (Fig.5(c)). The crumpled graphene on the crumpled substrate explains the delay of the strain build-up during the initial stretching stage as flattening of graphene is dominating; while the partial suspension is probably the reason for the η_c gradually approaching 1, as at higher strain when most of graphene tends to be flat but very locally some region are still crumpled but are flattening as the strain increases.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The effect of graphene crumpling which is usually the situation in composites, on the reinforcement of a polymer composite has been studied. It has been demonstrated micromechanically that the crumpling of graphene (or other flake-like fillers in composites) can lead to a strain release stage at the start of the tension, but stiffens as it flattens. It has also been demonstrated that the graphene flake may not only follow the crumpled morphology of the substrate but can also be partially suspended, probably due to the nature of graphene or the interface failure from the compression induced in the manufacturing stage. However, in both situations, the reduction of the reinforcement efficiency can be compromised during stretching as the elongation of the flake starts to dominate rather than flattening.

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